

Properties and Failure Prediction of Interply Hybrid Composites of Glass and Self-reinforced Polypropylene

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1- Background

- Hybridisation is achieved by combining two or more reinforcements in a single medium at interply level.
- Hybridisation is an efficient approach for exploiting the properties of both constituents synergically while alleviating their drawbacks.
- Pseudo-ductility is investigated in interply hybrids of self-reinforced polypropylene (SRPP) and glass reinforced polypropylene (GRPP) composites. In a pseudo-ductile hybrid composite, failure of the high stiffness layer does not lead to the failure of the whole structure.

2- Experimental Approach

1- GRPP laminae were prepared by placing one layer of glass fabric between two layers of polypropylene films.

2- SRPP fabrics were interleaved with GRPP laminae to make the assembly.

Fig1- Micrograph of the cross-section of a consolidated hybrid laminate

3- The assembly was placed between two platens for consolidation under heat (145°C) and pressure (70 bar).

5- References

- G. Czél and M. R. Wisnom, "Demonstration of pseudo-ductility in high performance glass/epoxy composites by hybridisation with thin-ply carbon prepreg," *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 52, pp. 23–30, 2013.
- M. Selezneva *et al.*, "Predicting Tensile Behaviour of Hybrid Carbon Fibre / Srpp Composites: How Far Can Analytical Models Take Us?," no. June, pp. 24–28, 2018.

6- Acknowledgment

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3- Results and Discussion

Fig2- Tensile moduli of hybrid laminates from experiment and calculations from the rule of mixtures (RoM).

Fig3- Stress-strain curves of the hybrid laminates with 10 layers of SRPP and different number of GRPP layers.

In the representative curve: [1,2]

$$\sigma_f = \frac{E_1 \varepsilon_{(gf)} t_1 + \sigma_2 t_2}{t_1 + t_2}$$

$$\sigma_{overall} = \frac{S_{SRPP} t_1}{t_1 + t_2}$$

$$G = \frac{\sigma^2 h^2}{4(E_1 t_1 + E_2 t_2)} - \frac{\sigma^2 h^2}{4E_1 t_1}$$

$$G = G_{IIC}, \quad \sigma = \sigma_d$$

- G_{IIC} mode II fracture toughness, kJ/m²
- S_{SRPP} : SRPP Ultimate strength, MPa
- $t_{1,2}$ Thickness of SRPP and GRPP, mm
- $E_{1,2}$ Tensile modulus of SRPP and GRPP, MPa
- $\sigma_{f,overall}$ Failure stress of GRPP, and whole structure, MPa

Table1 – Failure behaviour prediction for hybrid laminates tested in tension

Hybrid configuration	Experimental			Analytical			
	σ_f (MPa)	σ_d (MPa)	$\sigma_{f,overall}$ (MPa)	σ_f (MPa)	σ_d (MPa)	$\sigma_{f,overall}$ (MPa)	Criteria
5SR/1GRPP/5SR	78.9±0.72	82.8±2.37	208.6±5.01	81.9	120.8	192.4	$\sigma_d > \sigma_f$ Pseudo-ductile
5SR/2GRPP/5SR	83.2±1.27	81.8±1.64	182.9±5.37	87.8	86.68	171.6	$\sigma_d \approx \sigma_f$ Pseudo-ductile
5SR/3GRPP/5SR	100.5±1.48	91.6±1.35	176.9±4.01	92.8	70.98	165.3	$\sigma_d < \sigma_f$ Load drop
5SR/4GRPP/5SR	100.1±2.87	90.7±2.77	163.5±5.4	97.1	61.2	153.9	$\sigma_d < \sigma_f$ Load drop

4- Conclusions

- 28-45% increase in stiffness was achieved by interply hybridisation with 10 to 26 % of GRPP in SRPP/GRPP hybrid. [Fig 2]
- The critical thickness for pseudo-ductility was 0.28 mm equal to 19% of the whole thickness. [Table 1]
- The equation for the strain energy release rate was adopted to successfully predict the criteria to show pseudo-ductility. [Table 1]